

Cross-Cultural Adaptation and Validation of STEM Student Engagement Scale in Amharic for Ethiopian University Students

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Abstract

Student engagement in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education is among the essential elements in assessing students' academic performance and quality of education in general in higher education's institutes. It became very paramount to understand STEM students' engagement which is important driver for addressing the challenges related to quality, equity, and pertinence in STEM education; therefore, having an effective and reliable instrument to measure student engagement in STEM is essential.

This study aimed to structurally validate and check the cross-cultural robustness of the STEM Student Engagement Scale. In order to achieve this, a self-report questionnaire composed of the most pertinent conceptual elements and a previously existing instrument was used with 454 under graduate graduating class STEM students from two of Ethiopia's pioneering public universities, Hawassa University and Addis Ababa Science and Technology University. In addition to computing the global internal consistency, exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were performed. Identical factor structures were found across all of the subsamples. The findings advance current research by offering a tool that allows for the measurement of multifaceted STEM students' engagement in the context of Ethiopian universities in Amharic.

This scale contains psychometric properties and will be applied in research practice in the context.

Key words: Cross-cultural validation, Psychometric properties, STEM and Student engagement and Higher Education

Introduction

It is widely accepted that promoting student engagement is crucial for improving learning outcomes, academic achievement, and overall educational performance. It is also a fundamental component of the efforts made by educators, researchers, and policymakers to provide high-quality education. It shows how committed and involved students are in their learning activities, which include cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and agentic components (Fredricks et al., 2016; Reeve, 2012). According to Skinner et al. (2008) and Wang & Eccles (2013), motivated, persistent, and academically successful students are more likely to be involved.

Recognizing student engagement as a central cornerstone for improving the quality of education has facilitated the development of various theoretical frameworks and measurement tools designed to assess the construct in a valid and reliable manner. There are plenty of measuring tools to measure student engagement in university setups globally, but there is still a debate among scholars on which tool fully captures student engagement with addressing the entire construct to be measured. Among these, two notable instruments take a lion's share in recent literature, namely the traditional engagement tool introduced by Fredricks et al., (2016) and the instrument developed by Reeve and Tseng (2011) that highlights the importance of agentic engagement, which has gained considerable attention for its robust theoretical foundation and psychometric properties. The aforementioned tool assesses student engagement across multiple dimensions by holding four major forms of engagement: affective, cognitive, behavioral and agentic engagement.

Although these two instruments have been widely validated and employed across various educational contexts, their application has predominantly been limited to Western, individualistic cultures. However, STEM student engagement is not a permanent concept that can be measured consistently across different cultural settings. Given the global significance of STEM student

engagement, it is important to examine the effectiveness of these instruments in non-Western, collectivist cultures like Ethiopia, where educational and cultural practices differ considerably from Western one. Cultural factors have an essential role in determining student engagement in STEM fields by influencing learning styles, teaching methods, and perceptions of engagement within a specific cultural context (Holtbrügge & Mohr, 2010). Therefore, it is essential to validate STEM student engagement measures within Ethiopian universities to ensure their relevance and accurate interpretation. Cross-cultural validation is a key to ensuring that these measurement tools effectively capture the construct of STEM student engagement in diverse cultural and educational environments to enhance their usefulness and applicability (Ercikan et al., 2023).

In Ethiopian higher education, the importance of students' engagement in STEM fields is widely recognized for advancing the students' academic learning outcomes and general development in a country. However, no locally validated measurement tools that are tailored for Ethiopian university academics especially exist to measure STEM students' engagement. Due to this knowledge gap, we are unable to fully understand the idea of STEM student engagement in the Ethiopian context, which is a stepping stone to developing evidence-based interventions that will raise the standard of education. This study helps us to improve our understanding regarding student engagement in STEM fields in diverse cultural and educational contexts. In line with the growing body of research, it emphasizes the need for cross-cultural validation studies to provide culturally sensitive and contextually relevant instruments for evaluating STEM students' involvement (Holtbrügge & Mohr, 2010). In addition to providing guidance for the development of training programs and interventions that will increase the engagement of STEM students at Ethiopian universities, the research findings will contribute to the global understanding of student engagement and its importance in an educational context. Therefore, this study aims to validate the STEM student's engagement scale among university students in Ethiopia. Thus, this tool validation study is specifically intended to:

- Translate the original English version of the Mameli and Passini (2019) instrument into Amharic,
- Examine the Amharic version's psychometric qualities, including internal consistency, construct validity, component structure, and content validity.

- Assess the applicability of the instrument in a collectivist educational context, and
- Provide evidence on whether the multidimensional construct of STEM student engagement, as conceptualized by Mameli and Passini (2019), holds cross-cultural validity.

By addressing these objectives, this study aims to fill a gap in Ethiopian STEM student engagement research and add to the larger dialogue about culturally appropriate assessment methods in a construct under educational psychology.

Material and Methods

Study Design

This validation study used a cross-sectional research method, which is well known for its ability to gather, examine, and analyze data in a particular amount of time. Its capacity to provide a thorough snapshot of the traits, actions, and reactions of the targeted population at one particular moment led to the selection of this design. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the participants' perspectives, enabling researchers to identify patterns and correlations within the data. Ultimately, the findings can inform future interventions and policies aimed at enhancing outcomes in the studied area. By employing this approach, the study aimed to ensure efficiency in data collection while providing a clear and concise understanding of the variables under investigation. Additionally, the cross-sectional design allowed for the simultaneous examination of multiple factors, making it particularly suitable for validating the instrument and exploring its psychometric properties within the selected population.

Participants and sampling procedures of the study

Structural equation modeling requires careful consideration of sample size, especially when it comes to the quantity of observed variables (Jackson, 2003). Jackson (2003) highlights that researchers should consider the minimum sample size in relation to the number of model parameters that require statistical estimates (q) when using Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation. Jackson (2003) goes on to say that a 20:1 sample size to parameter ratio is ideal. Given that there are 23 total observed indicators in our investigation, a minimum sample size of 460 participants is required ($20 \times 23 = 460$). This ensures that the statistical analyses conducted

will yield reliable and valid results. Adhering to this guideline not only enhances the robustness of the findings but also helps mitigate potential issues related to over fitting or underestimating model complexity, From the target demographic, which includes undergraduate STEM students in their last year at the selected public universities of Ethiopia, Hawassa and Addis Ababa Science and Technology University, 460 students were selected. The two pioneer universities were selected by using a lottery method to choose students using basic random sampling from a list of all public universities in Ethiopia. Thus, the following formulas are used to determine the study sample size (Jackson, 2003 & Kothari, 2004). These calculations indicate that, in order to account for a 10% response error, the minimal sample size for this study is 460 ($460 + 46 = 486$). Therefore, Kothari's (2004) stratified proportional sample size allocation formula was used to accomplish proportionate allocation to the two universities, with 486 students representing the minimum sample size chosen from the target population.

Thus, 32 questionnaires' were not returned, leaving only 454 pupils participating. Then, the researchers conducted both confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA). One subgroup was subjected to EFA in order to investigate the EIS's underlying factor structure. To verify the factor structure and assess model fit indices, CFA was then performed on the remaining subgroup.

The validation study's participants were selected using the following inclusion criteria: a) they must be Ethiopian nationals (i.e., students enrolled in two prestigious Ethiopian universities), b) they must be enrolled in the fourth year of an undergraduate STEM program, and c) they must have indicated a desire to participate in the study. In the context of Ethiopian STEM education, this sample strategy made sure that the participants fairly reflected the target demographic, enabling a trustworthy validation of the tool.

Instrument

Two parts made up the instrument used in this validation research. Items in the first section were intended to collect demographic information about the participants, including age, gender, study field, year, parental educational status, residence status of students enrolled in university, and family monthly income. The second section comprises 23 items from the Mameli and Passini (2019) Student Engagement Instrument, which was developed to measure student

engagement across four dimensions by combining two dominant scales in student engagement literature. The scale includes 23 items categorized into four subscales:

Behavioral Engagement (5 items): Reflecting students' participation in academic activities and adherence to classroom rules. Emotional Engagement (5 items): Assessing how students feel about their educational experiences and how they interact with peers and teachers. Cognitive Engagement (6 items): Assessing pupils' dedication to learning, particularly their attempts to comprehend and become proficient in difficult subjects. Agentic Engagement (6 items): Measuring students' hands-on contribution to the learning process, such as expressing their preferences and reservations. Respondents were given a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 meant "strongly disagree" and 5 meant "strongly agree." The participants' levels of engagement in each of the four areas were thoroughly understood.

The mean scores were computed for every subscale to examine the prevalent aspects of student engagement. Higher scores on a given subscale suggested a greater propensity for those particular engagement aspects. The Mameli and Passini (2019) Engagement Instrument is among strong instruments which combine the traditional three forms of engagement (affective, cognitive, and behavioral) with the recently introduced agentic engagement scale, and it is widely validated in various contexts and has demonstrated strong psychometric properties. This instrument was selected for its ability to comprehensively assess student engagement in STEM fields in Ethiopian universities and its relevance to the academic context of Ethiopian university students. It offers a concise yet robust framework for evaluating student engagement in a culturally adaptable manner.

Procedures

During translation, adaptation, and data collection, a strict methodical procedure was followed to ensure the STEM Student Engagement Instrument's validity, reliability, and contextual relevance.

Step 1: Translation Process

When adapting an instrument, the first step is the translation of the instrument from the source language to the target one, that is, the language in which the new version will be used. It

is a complex process that requires tremendous care to ensure the final version is not only suitable for the new context but also consistent with the original version. As advised by Guillemin et al. (1993), the forward and backward translation methodology was used to translate the instrument from English into Amharic. The forward translation was carried out independently by two bilingual experts who are proficient in both Amharic and English. The primary researcher conducted a meeting to reconcile the two translated versions, ensuring that the Amharic version accurately preserved the original instrument's meaning and purpose. Unfamiliar with the original instrument, a third independent multilingual professional translated from Amharic to English backwards. Semantic equivalence was confirmed when the backward translated version and the original English version were examined and no notable differences were discovered.

Step 2: Content Validity Assessment

A group of eight experts evaluated the content validity of the STEM Student Engagement Instrument's original English version, as per Lawshe's (1975) recommendation. Lawshe's (1975), Content validity Ration (CVR) is a widely used method for measuring content validity in psychological and educational assessments more specifically in development and validation studies. Each item was evaluated for relevance, clarity, and appropriateness in the Ethiopian university STEM field's context. There was strong agreement among the experts, as evidenced by the Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.92 and the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) of 0.75 for all 23 items exceeding the acceptable threshold. Minor changes were made to improve clarity and contextual relevance in response to their input, and all 23 items were kept.

Step 3: Pre-Testing the Translated Instrument

The translated instrument was pre-tested with 50 fourth-year STEM students at Hawassa University. Participants provided their feedback on the clarity, comprehensibility, and cultural relevance of the measurement tool, as well as the ease of completing the questionnaire. Based on the already provided feedback from the experts, slight modifications were made to ensure the instrument was user-friendly and contextually appropriate. The final Amharic version demonstrated alignment with the original English version and was deemed ready for broader administration.

Step 4: Ethical Clearance and Permissions

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Hawassa University College of Education and Behavioral Science Ethical Committee. The Research Ethics Review Board at Hawassa University reviewed the study's purpose and granted permission to proceed.

Step 5: Participant Orientation and Data Collection

Target participants were identified and informed on the study's objectives and significance. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants after they were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Detailed instructions were given to the respondents on how to complete the questionnaire. The self-administered survey was then distributed, and participants completed the questionnaire at their own pace. Upon collection, all completed questionnaires were checked for accuracy and completeness. This systematic methodological approach will help to ensure the integrity and quality of the data by providing a concrete foundation for further psychometric evaluation of the instrument.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using STATA 17, deploying a two-step approach that consists of exploratory factor analysis (EFA) then followed by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to explore the underlying factor structure, assess relationships between factors, and evaluate model fit. Before the analysis, data accuracy was confirmed through a random check of 20% of the questionnaires, all of which were found to be acceptable. For the EFA, several criteria were established: factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were taken, a minimum of 60% explained variance was required, and KMO values needed to exceed 0.60. Additionally, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity had to be significant ($p < 0.05$), with factor loadings above 0.40 considered significant and factor correlations greater than 0.30 deemed acceptable. The results were also expected to align with a predefined four-factor model. Principal component extraction with varimax rotation was implemented under the assumption of factorial independence. In addition, items with cross-loadings greater than 0.40 on multiple factors were not included in the analysis, and real eigenvalues were compared to criterion values from Monte Carlo PCA for parallel analysis. The CFA assessed both absolute and incremental fit indices using maximum

likelihood (ML) estimation. A number of fit indices were taken into consideration, including the Normed Fit Index (NFI), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), which were both expected to be greater than 0.90, and CMIN/DF (intended to be less than 5).

Furthermore, a Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of less than 0.08 was preferred. In accordance with Hair et al. (2006), a model fit was deemed acceptable if three to four of these goodness-of-fit indices satisfied the predetermined thresholds. A number of metrics were used to evaluate validity and dependability. Composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) were compared in order to assess convergent validity. The square root of AVE for each subscale was compared with correlation coefficients from other subscales, and AVE was compared with both maximum shared squared variance (MSV) and average shared squared variance (ASV) in order to evaluate discriminant validity. Cronbach's alpha was used to test reliability; values greater than 0.7 indicated adequate item adequacy and internal consistency.

Ultimately, the entire sample size of $n = 454$ was split into two equal groups at random ($n = 227$ each). EFA was administered to the first group, and CFA was administered to the second. Subsamples did not differ significantly in terms of affiliation, age, gender, or field of study, according to statistical comparisons. In presenting the data analysis process, this all-inclusive methodology prioritizes objectivity and clarity while making sure that all important details are included in detail.

Results

In the present validation study, data were collected from 454 (female = 122 and male = 332) students who were randomly selected from Hawassa and Adiss Abeba Science and Technology University graduating-year undergraduate students and who properly fill all items in the scale. The mean age of the study participants was 22 years with a standard deviation of 1.217 (Table 1).

Table 1; Summary of sampled study participants' demographic characteristics (N = 454).

RN	Variables	Character	Frequency(f)	Percent (%)
1	Sex	Male	332	73.13
		Female	122	26.87
2	Field of study	Engineering	116	25.55
		Mathematics	110	24.23
		Technology	113	24.89
		Natural Science	115	25.33
3	Parents education level	No formal education	54	11.89
		Primary education	47	10.35
		Secondary education	46	10.13
		Diploma/technical training	67	14.76
		Bachelor degree	163	35.90
		Master's degree and above	77	16.96
4	Residence status	On-campus	428	94.27
		Off-campus	26	5.73

Results of the exploratory factor analysis

The correlation matrix, sample adequacy, and Bartlett's test of sphericity were examined prior to the execution of EFA. Inspection of the correlation matrix therefore showed that the coefficients of the majority of the items were ≥ 0.3 . With a KMO result of 0.934, the study's sample size was confirmed to be sufficient for exploratory factor analysis, surpassing the minimum threshold value of 0.60. Bartlett's test of sphericity supported the factorability of the correlation matrix and was significant ($\chi^2 = 5050.349$, $df = 253$, $p < 0.001$).

EFA was computed using principal component analysis and Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization, in which the absolute value of standardized factor loading > 0.40 was set to run factor extraction. Initially, this analysis showed a total of four (4) factor structures with Eigen values above 1.00 and total variance explained 50.40%. Scree plot analysis and Monte Carlo PCA for Parallel, which could compare the actual eigenvalues with their corresponding criteria values, revealed four (4) factor solutions that accounted for 40.60% of the variance. 64.33% was accounted for by factor 1 (behavioral), 40.62% by factor 2 (cognitive), 7.11% by factor 3 (emotional), and 1.58% by factor 4 (agentic).

As shown in Table 2 below, the rotation solution revealed the presence of four structures with a number of strong loading, and all items were substantially loaded on only one factor.

Accordingly, factor 1 (behavioural) includes items 20, 19, 21, 23, 22, and 16. Factor 2 (emotional) includes items 2, 3, 5, 4, and 1. Factor 3 (cognitive) includes items 14, 13, 12, 15, 17, 18, and 11. Factor 4 (agentic) includes items 9, 8, 10, 7, and 6. This confirmed that the optimal component for the Amharic version of the student engagement measure in Ethiopia was a four factor solution obtained from the total variance explained.

Table 2; Rotated results of the EFA on the Amharic version of the students' engagement scale.

Items	Structural Matrix			
	Factor 1 Behavioural	Factor 2 Emotional	Factor 3 Cognitive	Factor 4 Agnatic
Q2_C_20	0.7616			
Q2_C_19	0.7218			
Q2_C_21	0.6974			
Q2_C_23	0.6942			
Q2_C_22	0.6005			
Q2_C_16	0.4912			
Q2_C_2		0.7461		
Q2_C_3		0.7299		
Q2_C_5		0.7204		
Q2_C_4		0.7203		
Q2_C_1		0.6714		
Q2_C_14			0.6715	
Q2_C_13			0.6676	
Q2_C_12			0.6558	
Q2_C_15			0.5452	
Q2_C_17			0.5425	
Q2_C_18			0.5226	
Q2_C_11			0.5208	
Q2_C_9				0.7257
Q2_C_8				0.6601
Q2_C_10				0.6581
Q2_C_7				0.6398
Q2_C_6				0.5278
Proportion of variance explained (%)	32.106	20.654	6.721	5.028
Cumulative prop. variance explained (%)	32.106	28.743	19.821	37.891
KMO	0.934 > 0.6			
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (sig.)	0.000, < 0.001			

Extraction method; Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method; Varimax with Kaiser Normalization, Rotation Convergence in 10 iterations.

Results of the confirmatory factor analysis

The CFA was calculated using the data gathered from the second-half sample ($n = 227$) in addition to the EFA. Additionally, each scale's fundamental CFA assumptions were examined and determined to be viable. In this context, the factor structure of the Amharic version of the Students' Engagement Scale was evaluated with CFA using maximum likelihood evaluation of model fit indices and robust estimation techniques.

Fit was assessed using popular practical measures that have been suggested by a number of academics (e.g., Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013, Byrne, 2006; Hair et al., 2014a). Chi-square, ($CMIN < 5$), goodness of fit index ($GFI > 0.90$), adjusted goodness of fit ($AGFI > 0.90$), normed fit index ($NFI > 0.90$), comparative fit index ($CFI > 0.90$), and root mean square error of approximation ($RMSEA < 0.08$) are among them and need to be. According to the data gathered for this study, the initial Amharic version of the STEM student engagement measure had fit indices of χ^2 ($CMIN$) = 754.691, $CMIN/DF = 2.789$, $GFI = .883$, $AGFI = .956$, $CFI = .892$, and $RMSEA = .072$ on 23 items. According to Table 3 and Figure 1 below, every fit index in this initial model satisfies the model fit requirements.

This demonstrated that the model was adequate and didn't need to be refined. No items were removed from the model, and all of the items had low standardized residual covariance and high factor loadings (Table 3). As a result, it showed that the 23-item Amharic version of the student engagement scale is the most appropriate for gauging Ethiopian young adult university students' engagement in STEM.

Table 3. Result of CFA for the original and refined Amharic version students' engagement Scale.

Model	X^2/DF	X^2	GFI	CFI	NFI	AGFI	RMSEA	DF	P
Students engagement	2.789	754.691	.883	.892	.928	.956	.072	405	.000

Note. *CMIN = Model Chi-Square, GFI = Goodness of Fit Index; AGFI = Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index, CFI = comparative Fit Index; DF; Degree of freedom, RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation.*

Figure 1; Model fit indices summary of the students' engagement (Amharic version).

Convergent and discriminant validity

As briefly stated in Table 4, the convergent and discriminant validity of the STEM students engagement scale (Amharic version) was evaluated. The average variance explained (AVE) is greater than 0.5 in terms of convergent validity. Furthermore, it was discovered that every composite reliability (CR) value of the four-factor model was greater than 0.7. Each factor's CR value was higher than its AVE value. This suggests that the Amharic version of the student engagement scale has strong convergent validity. In terms of the scale's discriminant validity, the AVE values for each of the four student involvement components were greater than the MSV and ASV values. Furthermore, it was discovered that the correlation coefficient with the other dimensions was smaller than the square root of AVE for each of the four components (or dimensions). This indicates that the construct validity of the model is good (see Table 4).

Table 4: Convergent and Discriminant Validity of the Scale and the Correlation between Students' Engagement Subscales-Amharic Version.

Sub scales	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	1	2	3	4
1. Behavioral	0.867	0.692	.2803	.1382	.796			
2. Emotional	0.829	0.741	.0078	.0056	.0650	.872		
3. Cognitive	0.876	0.598	.2401	.1211	.423**	-.074	.822	
4. Agentic	0.798	0.671	.5302	.1094	.398**	-.036	.354**	.799

Note. CR = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted; MSV = maximum shared squared variance; ASV = average shared square variance.

Reliability of STEM Students' engagement Scale Amharic version

Table 5 below displays the Cronbach's alpha reliability of the students' engagement subscales or dimensions (Amharic version). The results demonstrate that the Cronbach alpha coefficients for all four dimensions are above the acceptable standard (>0.70). The estimated internal consistency for the STEM students engagement scale Amharic version was behavioural ($\alpha = .844$), emotional ($\alpha = .838$), cognitive ($\alpha = .707$), and agentic ($\alpha = .852$). This shows that the STEM students engagement scale Amharic version, has very good, acceptable internal consistency in the Ethiopian context with overall reliability of $\alpha = .932$.

Table 5: Reliability coefficient for the students' engagement Scale (Amharic version) after EFA and CFA

Variables	Number of items	Reliability coefficients(α)
Behavioral	5	0.844
Emotional	5	0.838
Cognitive	8	0.707
Agentic	5	0.852
Overall	23	0.932

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to translate and validate the 23-item STEM Student Engagement Scale into Amharic for use with university students in Ethiopia. The validation process, which included both exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, resulted in an overall reliability coefficient of 0.93. The EFA outcome demonstrated that each of the 23 items in the

Amharic version of the STEM Students engagement Scale exhibited robust loading, surpassing the threshold of 0.54. The loadings indicate a substantial and meaningful relationship between each item and its underlying factor. The results of the study confirmed that STEM Students engagement Scale derived from the total variance explained was replicated effectively within the Ethiopian eco-cultural context. This suggests that the STEM Students engagement Scale, is relevant and meaningful in understanding STEM students engagement among university students in Ethiopia. The findings confirm that the four-dimensional structure: behavioral, emotional, cognitive and agentic engagement holds true in the Ethiopian context, aligning with the conceptual framework underlying the original scale. The replication of these factors in the Ethiopian context provides support for the cross-cultural applicability of STEM Students engagement.

The results of this study align with many pieces of evidence gathered in different contexts, as shown by Assunção et al. (2020), Freiberg-Hoffmann et al. (2022), and Marcionetti & Zammiti (2023). The results of this study were consistent with earlier research conducted in various cultures, even when the amount of elements within each construct varied (Lessard et al., 2022). Disparities in translation, sample characteristics, and/or eco-cultural variances could be the cause of the variations in the number of items. These findings suggest that the 23-item Amharic version of STEM student engagement scale has demonstrated appropriate structural validity within the Ethiopian context. In other words, the modified scale has proven to be a relevant and reliable tool for evaluating STEM students' engagement in Ethiopian universities.

Our findings were consistent with previous research conducted in diverse contexts, This alignment of finding were observed in many studies (e.g., Heilporn et al., 2024; Purwono, 2023; Parra-Pérez et al., 2023). These results demonstrate how effective the Amharic version of STEM student engagement is when used with Ethiopian university students. Additionally, the results of the confirmatory factor analysis showed that the gathered data had outstanding convergent and discriminant validity, strongly supporting the proposed model. Furthermore, an evaluation of the Amharic version of the STEM student engagement scale's internal consistency showed strong reliability across the board, falling within an acceptable and very good range. The reliability values of the current investigation were in line with several previous studies, despite the fact that

internal consistency values are sensitive to the amount of items (Lessard et al., 2023; Sharif-Nia et al., 2023).

As the first attempt to validate the STEM student engagement scale specifically for Ethiopian university students, the researchers acknowledged that their study demonstrated encouraging positive psychometric properties that support the instrument's suitability within the Ethiopian eco-cultural context. This study successfully validated the STEM student engagement scale for Ethiopian universities, demonstrating its relevance in the Ethiopian setting.

It is critical to recognize the limitations of this study. One significant drawback of this study was that it was difficult to extrapolate the results to the whole university population because the respondents were only from two Ethiopian pioneer public universities. Therefore, it should be the goal of future research to include participants from Ethiopia's public and private universities. The Amharic version of the STEM student engagement scale would probably have stronger psychometric qualities with this larger sample.

Conclusion and recommendation

The 23-item STEM Student Engagement Scale was effectively translated and validated into Amharic in this study, demonstrating adequate construct validity and reliability. The results confirm that the four aspects of student engagement: behavioral, emotional, cognitive, and agentic are universally applicable in Ethiopian higher education environments. These results align with global studies, confirming that student engagement is a measurable and culturally adaptable construct. The Amharic version of the scale offers a valuable tool for educational researchers, practitioners, and policymakers aiming to enhance student engagement among university students in Ethiopia.

Based on the results of this study, it is vital to emphasize the validation STEM Students engagement Scale in a new cultural context. Furthermore, in this era of accelerated cultural diversity and the virtual age, it is imperative to emphasize that the use and significance of instruments like the STEM Students engagement Scale cannot be overstated. Therefore, in order to develop a comprehensive and robust STEM Students engagement Scale, it is necessary to conduct additional studies in different socio-cultural contexts.

References

- Assunção, H., Lin, S. W., Sit, P. S., Cheung, K. C., Harju-Luukkainen, H., Smith, T., ... & Marôco, J. (2020). University student engagement inventory (USEI): transcultural validity evidence across four continents. *Frontiers in Psychology, 10*, 2796.
- Assunção, H., Lin, S. W., Sit, P. S., Cheung, K. C., Harju-Luukkainen, H., Smith, T., ... & Marôco, J. (2020). University student engagement inventory (USEI): transcultural validity evidence across four continents. *Frontiers in Psychology, 10*, 2796.
- Byrne, B. (2006). *Structural equation modelling with EQS: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Ercikan, K., Por, H. H., & Guo, H. (2023). 11 Cross-cultural validity and comparability in assessments of complex constructs. *Innovating assessments to measure and support complex skills*, 190.
- Fredricks, J. A., Filsecker, M., & Lawson, M. A. (2016). Student engagement, context, and adjustment: Addressing definitional, measurement, and methodological issues. *Learning and instruction, 43*, 1-4.
- Freiberg-Hoffmann, A., Romero-Medina, A., Curione, K., & Marôco, J. (2022). Adaptación y validación transcultural al español del University Student Engagement Inventory. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología, 54*, 187-195.
- Freiberg-Hoffmann, A., Romero-Medina, A., Curione, K., & Marôco, J. (2022). Adaptación y validación transcultural al español del University Student Engagement Inventory. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología, 54*, 187-195.
- Guillemin, F., Bombardier, C., & Beaton, D. (1993). Cross-cultural adaptation of health-related quality of life measures: literature review and proposed guidelines. *Journal of clinical epidemiology, 46*(12), 1417-1432.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Multivariate data analysis* (7th ed.). Pearson New International Edition.
- Heilporn, G., Raynault, A., & Frenette, É. (2024). Student engagement in a higher education course: A multidimensional scale for different course modalities. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open, 9*, 100794.
- Holtbrügge, D., & Mohr, A. T. (2010). Cultural determinants of learning style preferences. *Academy of Management Learning & Education, 9*(4), 622-637.
- Jackson, D. L. (2003). Revisiting sample size and number of parameter estimates: Some support for the N: q hypothesis. *Structural equation modeling, 10*(1), 128-141.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Lawshe, C. H. (1975). A quantitative approach to content validity. *Personnel psychology, 28*(4).
- Lessard, A., Lopez, A., & Diallo, T. (2022). Validation of the French version of the student engagement instrument. *McGill Journal of Education, 57*(2), 77-91.

- Lessard, A., Lopez, A., & Diallo, T. (2022). Validation of the French version of the student engagement instrument. *McGill Journal of Education*, 57(2), 77-91.
- Mameli, C., & Passini, S. (2019). Development and validation of an enlarged version of the student agentic engagement scale. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 37(4), 450-463.
- Marcionetti, J., & Zammitti, A. (2024). Italian higher education student engagement scale (I-HESES): Initial validation and psychometric evidences. *Counselling Psychology Quarterly*, 37(3), 470-494.
- Marcionetti, J., & Zammitti, A. (2024). Italian higher education student engagement scale (I-HESES): Initial validation and psychometric evidences. *Counselling Psychology Quarterly*, 37(3), 470-494.
- Parra-Pérez, L. G., Valdés-Cuervo, A. A., Urías-Murrieta, M., Addo, R., Cota-Valenzuela, L. V., & García-Vázquez, F. I. (2023). Development and psychometric evidence of the Academic Engagement Scale (USAES) in Mexican college students. *Plos one*, 18(12), e0288012.
- Parra-Pérez, L. G., Valdés-Cuervo, A. A., Urías-Murrieta, M., Addo, R., Cota-Valenzuela, L. V., & García-Vázquez, F. I. (2023). Development and psychometric evidence of the Academic Engagement Scale (USAES) in Mexican college students. *Plos one*, 18(12), e0288012.
- Ramadhani, M. N., & Purwono, U. (2023). School engagement measure instrument adaptation. *Journal Research of Social Science Economics and Management*, 2(08).
- Ramadhani, M. N., & Purwono, U. (2023). School engagement measure instrument adaptation. *Journal Research of Social Science Economics and Management*, 2(08).
- Reeve, J. (2012). A self-determination theory perspective on student engagement. In *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 149-172). Boston, MA: Springer US.
- Reeve, J. (2013). How students create motivationally supportive learning environments for themselves: The concept of agentic engagement. *Journal of educational psychology*, 105(3), 579.
- Reeve, J., & Tseng, C. M. (2011). Agency as a fourth aspect of students' engagement during learning activities. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 36(4), 257-267.
- Sharif-Nia, H., Marôco, J., Rahmatpour, P., Ghahrani, N., Muhammad Ibrahim, F., Mohammad Ibrahim, M., & Kaveh, O. (2023). Psychometrics evaluation of the university student engagement inventory in online learning among Arab students. *BMC nursing*, 22(1), 158.
- Skinner, E. A., Pitzer, J. R., & Steele, J. S. (2016). Can student engagement serve as a motivational resource for academic coping, persistence, and learning during late elementary and early middle school?. *Developmental psychology*, 52(12), 2099.
- Tabachnick, B., & Fidell, I. S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics* (6th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Wang, M. T., & Eccles, J. S. (2013). School context, achievement motivation, and academic engagement: A longitudinal study of school engagement using a multidimensional perspective. *Learning and instruction*, 28, 12-23.